

Questions	totally agree	partially agree	somewhat agree	neutral	somewhat disgr	partially disagree	totally disagree
1.1 The artifact would help the project to be carried out optimizing time and resources (efficient)?	5	2	2	0	1	0	0
1.2 The artifact would help the project achieve its objective (effectively)?	4	4	1	1	0	0	0
1.3 Would the artifact help the project to be carried out in the best (effective) way?	3	2	2	3	0	0	0
1.4 Would the artifact help with common difficulties inherent in the problem identification phase?	5	3	1	1	0	0	0
1.5 Would the artifact help someone who is participating in identifying a problem in an AM project for the first time?	2	4	1	1	1	1	0
2.1 Using the artifact would improve my performance (you would do the activity faster) in identifying problems in projects	3	2	3	1	1	0	0
2.2 Using the artifact would increase my productivity (you would do the activity better and in a better time)	1	3	4	1	1	0	0
2.3 Using the artifact would increase my assertiveness in identifying problems to meet what the customer expects (you would do the activity better)	5	2	2	1	0	0	0
2.4 I find the system useful for identifying the problem	5	3	2	0	0	0	0
3.1 My interaction with the artifact is clear and understandable	1	4	1	2	2	0	0
3.2 Interacting with the artifact does not require much of my mental effort	1	3	1	1	3	1	0
3.3 I find the artifact easy to use	1	5	2	2	0	0	0
3.4 I find it easy to make the artifact be used for what I want	2	5	1	1	0	1	0
4.1 I could get the job done if there was no one around to tell me what to do	0	1	6	1	1	1	0
4.2 I could complete the work if I just had a resource or a brief explanation	1	4	2	2	1	0	0
4.3 I could complete the work if someone showed me how to do it first	5	3	2	0	0	0	0
4.4 I could complete the work if I had already used artifacts similar to this to identify problems	5	1	3	1	0	0	0
5.1 I have control over the artifact	1	2	1	2	3	1	0
5.2 In the artifact I have the necessary resources to identify the problem	4	4	1	1	0	0	0
5.3 Given the resources, opportunities, and knowledge needed to use the artifact, it would be easy to use it	4	4	1	1	0	0	0
5.4 The artifact is compatible with other systems and artifacts used in organization	3	3	0	4	0	0	0
6.1 I find the artifact pleasant to use	2	2	3	2	1	0	0
6.2 The process of using the artifact is enjoyable	3	1	3	3	0	0	0
6.3 I have fun using the artifact	2	0	1	4	3	0	0
7.1 In my work, the use of the artifact is important	3	3	3	1	0	0	0
7.2 In my work, the use of the artifact is relevant	6	3	1	0	0	0	0
7.3 The use of the artifact is relevant to my tasks in the project	4	6	0	0	0	0	0
8.1 The quality of the artifact output is high	3	2	3	2	0	0	0
8.2 I classify the artifact's results as excellent	2	2	4	2	0	0	0
8.3 I would have no difficulty telling others about the results of using the artifact	3	3	3	1	0	0	0
8.4 I believe I could communicate to others the consequences of using the artifact	2	4	4	0	0	0	0
8.5 The results of using the artifact are apparent to me	4	2	3	1	0	0	0
8.6 I would have a hard time explaining why using the artifact might or might not be beneficial	0	0	1	1	2	4	2
9.1 If I have access to the artifact, I intend to use it	1	3	2	4	0	0	0
9.2 Given that I had access to the artifact, I anticipate that I would use it	2	1	5	2	0	0	0
9.3 I plan to use the artifact in upcoming projects	1	4	2	2	1	0	0